

IN VITRO ANTI-CANCER ACTIVITY OF SIDDHA FORMULATION VEERA RASA PADHANGAM (VRP) IN LUNG CANCER (A549) CELL LINE USING MTT ASSAY

G. Vaishnu Devi^{*1}, K. Vaishnavadevi^{*2}, R. Antony Duraichi^{*3}, G. Essaky Pandian^{*4}

^{*1,2}PG Scholar, Department of PG Gunapadam, Government Siddha Medical College and Hospital, Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli.

^{*3}Assistant Professor, Department of PG Gunapadam, Government Siddha Medical College and Hospital, Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli.

^{*4}HOD & Professor, Department of PG Gunapadam, Government Siddha Medical College and Hospital, Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli.

Article Received on 20 Sept. 2025,
Article Revised on 10 October 2025,
Article Published on 01 Nov. 2025,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17470964>

*Corresponding Author

G. Vaishnu Devi

PG Scholar, Department of PG
Gunapadam, Government Siddha
Medical College and Hospital,
Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli.

How to cite this Article: G. Vaishnu Devi*, K. Vaishnavadevi*, R. Antony Duraichi*, G. Essaky Pandian* (2025). IN VITRO ANTI-CANCER ACTIVITY OF SIDDHA FORMULATION VEERA RASA PADHANGAM (VRP) IN LUNG CANCER (A549) CELL LINE USING MTT ASSAY World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(11), 426-433.
This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

In India, one in nine people are likely to develop cancer in his/her lifetime. Lung cancer is the leading cause of cancer death world wide. In siddha system of medicine the Metalo mineral formulations are very vital. These are effective in very minimal dose, challenges incurable diseases, increased bio availability, shelf life is higher when compared to herbal products, therapeutic efficacy is high, quick remedy, adoptogenecity (the same drug can be successfully used for various diseases). There are various effective Siddha medicines mentioned in Siddha classical literature and manuscripts for “Puttru”. Therefore identification and scientific validation of an effective siddha Metalo mineral drug to treat Lung cancer is very essential in this current world. In that aspect there is a preparation in the literature of YAKOBU VAITHIYA SINTHAMANI 700 (pg.No.124) VEERA RASA PADHANGAM which is indicated for PUTRU, “VEERA RASA PADHANGAM” is one of the metalo mineral medicine

having Anticancer property, This study investigates the in vitro anti-cancer activity of the Siddha formulation Veera Rasa Padhangam (VRP) against lung cancer (A549) cell line using the MTT assay. The results show that VRP exhibits promising anti-cancer activity, with a significant decrease in cell viability and an increase in cell death at varying concentrations. The IC₅₀ value was found to be 329.9 ± 22.5 µg/ml, indicating the potential therapeutic efficacy of VRP against lung cancer.

KEYWORD: Lung cancer, Puttru, MTT assay, Vera rasa padhangam.

INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer continues to be the foremost cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide, with projections estimating a 67% increase in incidence by 2040. The grave nature of the disease is further underscored by its low 5-year survival rate of 10-20%. Despite advances in conventional therapies, there is a growing interest in exploring traditional medicine and natural compounds for cancer treatment. Siddha medicine, a traditional system of medicine in India, offers a rich repository of herbal formulations with potential therapeutic benefits. Veera Rasa Padhangam (VRP) is a Siddha formulation that has been used in traditional medicine for various ailments. This study aims to evaluate the in vitro anti-cancer activity of VRP against lung cancer (A549) cell line using the MTT assay.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Trial Drug

The drugs VEERAM and URUKKU are purified and grinded well in the kalvam (stone mortar), continuously until mercury was expelled out from the mixture, the mixture was subjected to the process of sublimation for 3 saman (9hrs), after self cooling the sublimated product was again subjected to kuppi puda karuvi (manal maraivu pudam) for 4 samam (12hrs). The final product was weighed and stored in glass vessel.

Invitro Anti-Cancer activity

Preparation of test solutions

For anti-proliferative studies, serial dilutions of test formulation (10, 50, 100 and 200 µg/ml) were prepared.

Lung cancer (A549) cell culture and media

Lung cancer (A549) cell lines were procured from NCCS, stock cells was cultured in medium supplemented with 10% inactivated Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), penicillin (100 IU/ml), streptomycin (100 µg/ml) in an humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂ at 37°C until confluent. The cell was dissociated with TPVG solution (0.2 % trypsin, 0.02 % EDTA, 0.05 % glucose in PBS). The viability of the cells are checked and centrifuged. Further 50,000 cells / well was seeded in a 96 well plate and incubated for 24 hrs at 37°C, 5% CO₂ incubator.

Source of reagents: DMEM, FBS, Pen strip, Trypsin procured from Himedia.

Anti- proliferation assay

The monolayer cell culture was trypsinized and the cell count was adjusted to 1.0×10^5 cells/ml using respective media containing 10% FBS. To each well of the 96 well microtiter plate, 100µl of the diluted cell suspension (50,000cells/well) was added. After 24 h, when a partial monolayer was formed, the supernatant was flicked off, washed the monolayer once with medium and 100µl of different test concentrations of test drugs were added on to the partial monolayer in microtiter plates. The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 48hrs in 5% CO₂ atmosphere. After incubation the test solutions in the wells were discarded and 100µl of MTT (5 mg/10 ml of MTT in PBS) was added to each well. The plates were incubated for 4h at 37°C in 5% CO₂ atmosphere. The supernatant was removed and 100µl of DMSO was added and the plates were gently shaken to solubilize the formed formazan. The absorbance was measured using a microplate reader at a wavelength of 570 nm. The percentage growth inhibition was calculated using the following formula and concentration of test drug needed to inhibit cell growth by 50% (IC₅₀) values is generated from the dose-response curves for each cell line.

$$\text{Survival rate (\%)} = \frac{A_{\text{sample}} - A_{\text{b}}}{A_{\text{c}} - A_{\text{b}}} \times 100$$

IC₅₀ Value

The half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) is a measure of the effectiveness of a compound in inhibiting biological or biochemical function. This quantitative measure indicates how much of a particular drug or other substance (inhibitor) is needed to inhibit a given biological process (or component of a process, i.e. an enzyme, cell, cell receptor or microorganism) by half.

The IC₅₀ of a drug can be determined by constructing a dose-response curve and examining the effect of different concentrations of antagonist on reversing agonist activity. IC₅₀ values can be calculated for a given antagonist by determining the concentration needed to inhibit half of the maximum biological response of the agonist. IC₅₀ values for cytotoxicity tests were derived from a nonlinear regression analysis (curve fit) based on sigmoid dose response curve.

MTT Assay

The *in vitro* determinations of anti-proliferative effects of the test formulation have been performed by counting viable cells after staining with a vital dye. The MTT system is a means of measuring the activity of living cells via mitochondrial dehydrogenases. The MTT method is simple, accurate and yields reproducible results. The key component is (3-[4, 5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2, 5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide) or MTT, is a water soluble tetrazolium salt upon incubation MTT is converted to an insoluble purple formazan by cleavage of the tetrazolium ring by mitochondrial dehydrogenase enzymes of viable cells. The resulting colored solution is spectrophotometrically measured. An increase or decrease in cell number results in a concomitant change in the amount of formazan formed, indicating the degree of cytotoxicity caused by the test material.

Table 1: Effect of Test drug VRP on Cell viability of Lung cancer (A549) cell line.

S.No	Concentration in µg/ml	% cell Viability
1	10	97.33 ± 1.595
2	50	86.06 ± 2.116
3	100	79.65 ± 0.8194
4	200	69.34 ± 1.451

Figure 1.

Table 2: Effect of Test drug VRP on Cell death of Lung cancer (A549) cell line.

S.No	Concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	% cell Death
1	10	20.49 ± 0.39
2	50	31 ± 1.483
3	100	43.82 ± 1.60
4	200	59.59 ± 0.80

Figure 2.**Table 3: IC 50 Value of VRP.**

IC 50 Value of VRP	$329.9 \pm 22.5 \mu\text{g/ml}$
--------------------	---------------------------------

Figure 4: Test Drug VRP - 10 μg .

Figure 5: Test Drug VRP - 50 µg.

Figure 6: Test Drug VRP - 100 µg.

Figure 7: Test Drug VRP - 200 µg.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In-vitro anti-cancer evaluation of test drug VRP on the cell viability against Lung cancer (A549) cell line was performed at varying concentration ranges from 10 to 200 µg/ml. The result obtained from the study reveals that the percentage of cell viability of Lung cancer

(A549) cell line decrease with increase in concentration of the test drug VRP. Least viability of cell was observed at the concentration of 200 μ g/ml shows 69.34 \pm 1.451%, followed by this 100 μ g/ml shows 79.65 \pm 0.81 similarly 50 and 10 μ g/ml shows 86.06 \pm 2.11 and 97.33 \pm 1.595 % cell viability in MTT assay. The corresponding IC50 value was found to be 329.9 \pm 22.5 μ g/ml. It was concluded from the result of the present study that the formulation VRP possess promising anti-cancer activity. The results show that VRP exhibits a concentration-dependent decrease in cell viability and an increase in cell death. The percentage of cell viability decreased from 97.33 \pm 1.595% at 10 μ g/ml to 69.34 \pm 1.451% at 200 μ g/ml. The corresponding IC50 value was found to be 329.9 \pm 22.5 μ g/ml. The decrease in cell viability and increase in cell death suggest that VRP may be a promising therapeutic agent for lung cancer treatment. Further studies are needed to elucidate the underlying mechanisms and to explore the potential therapeutic applications of VRP.

Statistics

The calculated G*Power (t-test) value indicates that the study has sufficient power (80.44%) to detect a medium to large effect size.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study shows that VRP exhibits promising anti-cancer activity against lung cancer (A549) cell line. The results suggest that VRP may be a potential therapeutic agent for lung cancer treatment, and further studies are warranted to explore its therapeutic applications.

Conflict of interest: nil.

REFERENCES

1. G. Ramasamy kon. 1951, Rama devar enra Yakobu aruli seitha vaithiya sinthamani 700, 5th publication by E. Rama gurusamy konar son (pg.no.124,125).
2. Dr. R. Thyagarajan, Gunapadam Thathu Jeeva Vaguppu part 2 & amp; 3, Department of Indian medicine and Homeopathy, Chennai 106.
3. Bray F, Ferlay J, Soerjomataram I, et al. Global cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA Cancer J Clin.*, 2018; 68: 394-424. 10.3322/caac.21492 [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

4. Boukamp P., Petrussevska R. T., Breitkreutz D., Hornung J., Markham A., Fusenig N. E. Normal keratinization in a spontaneously immortalized aneuploid human keratinocyte cell line. *The Journal of Cell Biology*, 1988; 106(3): 761–771.
5. Gonzalez, R. J. and Tarloff, J.B. (2001) Evaluation of hepatic sub cellular Fractions for alamar blue and MTT reductase activity. *Toxicology in vitro*, 15: 259-9.